

Terpenoids. Part XCII. A New Route Towards the Synthesis of γ -Bisabolene

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Manuscript received 9 September 1974; revised 28 February 1975; accepted 18 March 1975

Wittig olefination of 4-(4',4'-ethylenedioxcyclohexylidene)-pentanal furnishes 2-methyl-6-(4',4'-ethylenedioxcyclohexylidene)-hept-2-ene which when submitted to deketalisation, followed by Grignard reaction with methylmagnesium iodide, yields 2-methyl-6-(4'-hydroxy-4'-methylcyclohexylidene)-hept-2-ene. Dehydration of this alcohol provides the sesquiterpene hydrocarbon γ -bisabolene.

BISABOLENES, a very important group of monocyclic sesquiterpene hydrocarbons, offer a variety of interesting members having olefinic double bonds in different and specific positions. Recently, the syntheses of β -bisabolene, γ -bisabolene and iso-bisabolene have been reported¹⁻⁶. The present communication embodies an elegant and unambiguous synthesis of γ -bisabolene(I), which has been found in a number of essential oils⁷⁻¹⁰. The scheme of the reactions employed in the projected synthesis is depicted in chart I.

The allylic alcohol(II) was procured according to the procedure reported in literature¹¹ and converted into the corresponding mesylate (III) with mesyl chloride¹² and triethylamine in anhydrous methylene chloride in 80% yield. Alkylation of (III) with diethylmalonate, using potassium tert. butoxide as base, in tert. butyl alcohol, gave the diester (IV) in 69% yield. The diester(IV) when heated with a mixture of sodium chloride, water and DMSO¹³ at 165°, furnished the monoester(V) in 70% yield. Reduction of the monoester(V) with LAH to the corresponding ketal-alcohol (VI) and subsequent oxidation with chromium trioxide-pyridine complex¹⁴ in dry methylene chloride yielded the aldehyde (VII).

The aldehyde(VII) when submitted to Wittig reaction¹⁵ with isopropylidene-triphenylphosphorane in DMSO afforded the compound(VIII) in 80% yield.

The ketal(VIII) was deketalised with 10% hydrochloric acid in acetone and the ketone (IX) so obtained was purified by column chromatography. Grignard reaction on the ketone(IX) with methylmagnesium iodide in dry ether gave the alcohol (X) which on dehydration with POCl₃/pyridine at 0°, furnished γ -bisabolene(I).

The hydrocarbon(I) was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina and purity checked by TLC. The identity of the synthetic product with

that of the natural γ -bisabolene was established through comparison of its IR and NMR spectra¹⁶.

Chart I

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra (thin liquid films) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infracord. NMR spectrum was taken in carbon tetrachloride (10% solution) on a Varian A60A spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard.

1-Mesyloxy-2-(4',4'-ethylenedioxcyclohexylidene)propane(III) :

To a stirring mixture of the allylic alcohol (II, 10.5 g) and triethylamine (5.9 g) in anhydrous methylene chloride (250 ml), maintained at -5° was added

mesyl chloride (6.7 g) dropwise, over a period of ten minutes and stirring was continued at this temperature for half an hour. The reaction mixture was treated with ice cold water and extracted with methylene chloride, washed with cold 10% hydrochloric acid, saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, brine solution and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. Removal of the solvent afforded the mesylate (III, 11.4 g, 80%). The mesylate was used as such for the next operation. I.R. spectrum showed no absorption in the hydroxy region.

Ethyl 2-carbethoxy-4-(4'-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexylidene)pentanoate (IV) :

Potassium tert.-butoxide was prepared from potassium metal (1.7 g) and excess of tert. butyl alcohol (250 ml). To this was added diethyl malonate (7 g) and the reaction mixture refluxed for one hour, cooled and the mesylate (III, 11 g) was added. The contents were refluxed for 8 hr and then the excess of tert. butyl alcohol was removed under vacuum. The residue was decomposed with water and extracted thoroughly with ether, dried (Na_2SO_4), solvent removed and distillation of the residue under vacuum yielded the diester (IV, 9.6 g, 69%); b.p. $170^\circ/10$ mm. ν_{max} $1720\text{--}1735\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (diester, $>\text{C}=\text{O}$), $1060, 1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ketal). (Found : C, 63.25; H, 8.35. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 63.51; H, 8.29%).

Ethyl 4-(4'-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexylidene)pentanoate (V) :

A mixture of the diester (IV, 9.5 g), sodium chloride (2 g), water (2 ml) and DMSO (50 ml) was heated at 165° for 5 hr. The solvent was removed under diminished pressure and the residue poured into water, extracted thoroughly with ether and dried. The solvent was expelled and distillation of the residue under vacuum afforded the monoester (V, 5.25 g, 70%); b.p. $154^\circ\text{--}156^\circ/10$ mm. ν_{max} 1725 cm^{-1} (ester, $>\text{C}=\text{O}$); $1060, 1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ketal). (Found : C, 67.25; H, 9.15. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 67.13; H, 9.02%).

4-(4',4'-Ethylenedioxy-cyclohexylidene)pentanol (VI) :

To a slurry of LAH (900 mg) in dry ether (100 ml) was added slowly, with stirring, the ester (V, 5 g) in ether (25 ml). The stirring was continued overnight and the reaction mixture was cooled in ice bath and decomposed with saturated solution of sodium potassium tartarate. The product was extracted with ether and dried. Removal of the solvent and subsequent distillation under reduced pressure gave the alcohol (VI, 3.2 g, 75%); b.p. $160^\circ/8$ mm. ν_{max} $3350, 1045\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Primary $-\text{OH}$), 1060 cm^{-1} (ketal). (Found : C, 68.68; H, 9.95. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 68.99; H, 9.80%).

4-(4',4'-Ethylenedioxy-cyclohexylidene)pentanol (VII) :

Powdered chromium trioxide (8.2 g) was added in small lots to a stirring mixture of pyridine (13 g.) and methylene chloride (200 ml) maintained between $10^\circ\text{--}15^\circ$. The stirring was continued for an additional

period of 15 min. at room temperature (25°) and to this was added the alcohol (IV, 3.1 g) in dry methylene chloride (10 ml) in a single instalment. The reaction mixture was stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr and the contents poured into iced water. The organic layer was separated, washed with cold water and dried (anhy. CaCl_2). Removal of the solvent, followed by distillation under vacuum, provided the aldehyde (VIII, 2.2 g, 74%); b.p. $135^\circ/7\text{--}8$ mm. ν_{max} 2720 cm^{-1} (Aldehydic C-H), 1715 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1060 cm^{-1} (ketal). (Found : C, 69.65; H, 8.85. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 69.61; H, 8.99%).

2-Methyl-6-(4',4'-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexylidene)-hept-2-ene (VIII) :

Isopropylidetriphenylphosphorane was prepared from sodium hydride (0.55 g, 50%) in DMSO (6 ml), isopropyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (4.9 g) in DMSO (12 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere. To this was added the aldehyde (VII, 2.1 g) in THF (5 ml.). The contents were stirred overnight and then warmed for half an hour at 40° . The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice and extracted with pet. ether ($40^\circ\text{--}60^\circ$), dried and solvent removed. Distillation of the residue under reduced pressure afforded the compound (VIII, 1.8 g, 80%). ν_{max} 1050 cm^{-1} (ketal),

H
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850 and 835 cm^{-1} ($-\text{C}=\text{C}-$). (Found : C, 76.68; H, 10.50. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 76.75; H, 10.47%).

2-Methyl-6-(4'-oxocyclohexylidene)-hept-2-ene (IX) :

A mixture of the ketal (VIII, 1.7 g), hydrochloric acid (7 ml, 10%) and acetone (25 ml) was stirred for 4 hr at room temperature. The reaction mixture was diluted with brine solution, extracted thoroughly with ether and dried. Removed the solvent and took the residue in ether, dried and again removed the solvent. Distillation of the product under vacuum yielded the ketone (IX, 1.1 g, 78%); b.p. $130^\circ/8$ mm. The ketone was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina, using pet. ether ($40^\circ\text{--}60^\circ$) : benzene :: 70 : 30 as the eluent. ν_{max} 1705 cm^{-1} ($-\text{C}=\text{O}$). (Found : C, 81.55; H, 10.82.

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 $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$ requires C, 81.50; H, 10.75%).

2-Methyl-6-(4'-hydroxy-4'-methylcyclohexylidene)-hept-2-ene (X) :

Grignard reagent was prepared from magnesium turnings (150 mg) and methyl iodide (1 g) in anhydrous ether (25 ml). To the cooled Grignard reagent was added, in drops, the ketone (IX, 1 g) in dry ether (5 ml) with shaking. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 6 hr and then refluxed for 15 min, cooled and decomposed with saturated ammonium chloride solution. The product was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried. The solvent removal, followed by vacuum distillation, afforded the alcohol (X, 900 mg, 82%); b.p. $135^\circ/7$ mm. ν_{max} 3400 and 1110 cm^{-1} ($-\text{OH}$, secondary). (Found : C, 80.95; H, 11.76. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}$ requires C, 81.02; H, 11.79%).

2-Methyl-6-(4'-methylcyclohex-3'-enylidene)-hept-2-ene (I):

To a solution of the alcohol (X, 800 mg) in anhydrous pyridine (4.8 ml) at 0° was added under stirring phosphorus oxychloride (0.76 g) dropwise. The stirring was continued for 2 hr and the reaction mixture was cooled, decomposed with iced water and extracted with ether. The combined ether extracts were dried after washing with water. The solvent was removed and the residue chromatographed over neutral alumina, eluting with pet. ether (40°-60°). Distillation under diminished pressure furnished the hydrocarbon(I); b.p. 132°-135°/11-12 mm. The purity of the hydrocarbon (I) was checked by TLC which showed single visible spot (solvent system, *n*-hexanebenzene, 1:1). η_D^{25} 1.4928. (lit.¹⁶ η_D^{21} 1.4923). (Found: C, 88.10; H, 11.82. C₁₅H₂₄ requires, C, 88.16; H, 11.84%).

IR spectrum of the synthetic product showed prominent absorption peaks at 1650, 1450, 1360, 1255, 1230, 1140, 1110, 1075, 1050, 1020, 975, 935, 915, 890, 855, 835, 790, 770 and 720 cm⁻¹, comparable to those reported in literature¹⁶. Finally the identity of the synthetic sample was established from its NMR spectrum which exhibited characteristic signals at $\tau = 4.70$ (1 H, vinylic ring proton); 5 (1 H, vinylic proton); 7.35 (2 H, broad, doubly allylic ring methylene); 7.76 (2 H, doublet, allylic methylene); 8.0 (6 H, methylene); 8.37 (9 H, vinylic methyls); 8.44 (3 H, allylic methyl).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for awarding a junior research fellowship to one of them (MLS). Also grateful thanks are due to Dr. Sijan Singh, B.H.U., Varanasi for the record of the NMR spectrum.

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